

QUIZ**LAST NAME: JANNEH****FIRST NAME: MAIMUNA****PROGRAM CODE: MSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (footnotes)
The author did use Zotero to insert references
The author used the following software: MSWord 2007 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: AN ASSESSMENT OF KEY POINTS

1. **What is the difference between single and double quotation marks according to European Commission rule?**
 - There is no difference except that a single inverted comma is used for a single quotation and a double inverted comma is used for double quotation
 - A single quotation is used to divide a sentence into two, while a double quotation is used to emphasize the quoted statement
 - Single quotation marks are used to signal direct speech and verbatim quotes and also used to identify words and phrases that are not themselves quotes but to which you wish to draw attention as lexical items; while double quotation marks are used for quotations within these¹**
 - The single quotation mark is used for foreign words in English text while double quotation marks are used for translated titles of work that appear only in a foreign language

¹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed. (European Commission Directorate-General for Translation, 2011), 26.

2. **Why should you put footnote references in brackets before punctuation?**

- To separate the footnote from the punctuation
- To achieve uniformity across language versions²**
- To create a difference between footnotes and endnotes
- To number the footnotes in order

3. **Opinions must be avoided in research writing because objectivity is the key. Why are opinions not allowed in the findings?**

- To give a better fact approach to research because the opinions of different scientists can differ³**
- Opinions are not important in non-technical papers
- Opinions do not emphasize a research report
- Opinions waste researcher's time

4. **What is the risk of including Anthropomorphism in research writing?**

- It does not attribute to human motivation, characteristics, or behavior
- It simplifies research and enhances the understanding
- It is usually not factual
- It can cause ambiguity and confuse readers⁴**

² European Commission, 47.

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 4* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 7.

⁴ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 10.

5. **What is the purpose of citing a source in writing?**

- To increase the volume of the writing
- To recognize the author, show evidence of the authenticity of the information, convince readers about the reliability of the research method, to provide other researchers with resources to expand on the work or conduct different research, and to avoid plagiarism and its charges⁵**
- To gain recognition of one's work
- To earn more grades and reward for the research

6. **What are the two most common citation styles?**

- Author-date and bibliography⁶**
- Bibliography and notes-bibliography
- Reference list and bibliography
- Footnotes and endnotes

7. **Effective writing has the following traits:**

- Interesting, informative, clear, and captivating
- Detailed, pleasing, specific, appropriate language, and caring
- Stimulating ideas, logical organization, engaging voice, original word choice, smooth reading sentences, and correct and accurate⁷**

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*: (University of Chicago Press, 2013), 86.

⁶ Turabian, 87.

⁷ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000* (Wilmington, Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 31–33.

- Smooth flowing sentences, good grammar, proper spelling, and correct punctuation

8. **What is the final step in the writing process?**

- Publishing⁸**
- Referencing
- Editing
- Saving

9. **Where do the US and the UK place punctuation for a quotation?**

- The UK places the punctuation inside the quote while the US places it outside the quote
- Both the US and the UK place the punctuation inside the quote
- If the punctuation is a period, they place it inside the quote and place it outside the quote when it is a question mark
- The US places the punctuation inside the quote while the UK places it outside the quote⁹**

10. **What is the most important thing to avoid in writing papers?**

- Plagiarism¹⁰**
- Quotations
- Recognition

⁸ Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer, 48.

⁹ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1* (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015), 7.

¹⁰ EUCLID, 8.

Proofreading

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